

THE EFFECT OF SALARY AND WORK INSURANCE ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE WITH JOB SATISFACTION AS A MEDIATION VARIABLE IN A STUDY AT PT PATRIOT INTAN ABADI

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Abstraction

In an era of increasingly competitive business competition, employee performance is a key factor in organizational success because it plays a direct role in achieving company goals and sustainability. One effort that companies can make to improve employee performance is through compensation management, especially salary and work insurance, by paying attention to the level of employee job satisfaction. This study aims to analyze the effect of salary and work insurance on employee performance with job satisfaction as a mediating variable at PT Patriot Intan Abadi. This study uses a quantitative approach with a causal design. Data were obtained through a survey using questionnaires distributed to all employees of PT Patriot Intan Abadi involved in the chicken farming project. The study population was 120 employees and all of them were used as research samples. The data analysis technique used Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with the help of AMOS 26.00 software. The results of the study indicate that salary has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction (estimate = 0.208; p-value = 0.019), and work insurance has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction (estimate = 0.353; p-value 0.000). Job satisfaction is also proven to have a positive and significant effect on employee performance (estimate = 0.245; p-value = 0.015). However, salary does not have a significant direct effect on employee performance (estimate = 0.139; p-value = 0.107), while work insurance has a positive and significant effect on employee performance (estimate = 0.391; p-value 0.000). These findings indicate that job satisfaction acts as a full mediating variable in the relationship between salary and employee performance, as well as a partial mediating variable in the relationship between work insurance and employee performance.

Keywords: *Salary, Employment Insurance, Job Satisfaction, Employee Performance*

INTRODUCTION

In the era of globalization and the rapidly evolving digital economy, organizational competitiveness depends heavily on their ability to effectively manage human resources. Employee performance is a key indicator of organizational success because it is directly linked to the achievement of strategic goals and operational sustainability. Companies that can create a productive work environment through appropriate HR management strategies will have a sustainable competitive advantage (Dessler, 2018). Human resources are a vital asset for any company in achieving its goals. A company's success is largely determined by the quality and performance of its employees. Good employee performance will help the company achieve its stated goals effectively and efficiently. One of the most significant factors influencing employee performance is compensation, particularly salary. Salary not only provides financial rewards for employee contributions but also serves as a primary source of motivation for increasing productivity. Research by Zailani and Artanto (2024) shows that salary has a significant positive influence on employee performance, both directly and through job satisfaction as a mediating variable. Employees who feel financially rewarded tend to demonstrate higher commitment and loyalty to their organization (Zailani & Artanto, 2024). Job satisfaction acts as a mediating factor that strengthens the influence of compensation on performance. When employees are satisfied with their salary and insurance, they tend to be more motivated to perform well. Previous research also shows that job satisfaction can increase employee loyalty, reduce turnover, and create stability within an organization. This is especially important in a dynamic and challenging work environment.

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Figure 1. Employee Performance Assessment Data at PT Patriot Intan Abadi 2023

Source: PT patriot Intan Abadi

Based on the results of the employee performance assessment at PT Patriot Intan Abadi, it is clear that the majority of employees are in the suboptimal performance category. Of the 39 employees, only 5 (12.8%) showed excellent performance, and 7 (17.9%) showed good performance. Meanwhile, 12 employees (30.8%) were categorized as having adequate performance and 15 employees (38.5%) had poor performance. These findings indicate that the majority of employees (69.3%) have not achieved the expected performance standards. This condition may reflect the existence of internal problems that need to be evaluated, particularly related to factors that influence productivity and work motivation. One important factor that can influence performance is the level of job satisfaction, which is significantly influenced by the salary system and job security, such as insurance. According to Zeithaml, Bitner, and Gremler (2022), fair compensation and adequate job security are key components in creating a productive and loyal work environment. Furthermore, Kim, Lee, and Kim (2018) emphasized that dissatisfaction with the reward system can lead to low employee motivation and engagement, ultimately negatively impacting performance. In another study, Liu and Shieh (2021) also revealed that inadequate attention to employee well-being can reduce employee loyalty and work enthusiasm. This demonstrates the importance of job satisfaction as a mediating variable that bridges the influence of salary and job insurance on employee performance (Sweeney & Soutar, 2018). This phenomenon underscores the importance of salary and insurance in building employee satisfaction, which directly impacts their performance. PT Patriot Intan Abadi has a significant opportunity to improve the operational results of its chicken project through a balanced policy of salary and insurance coverage. This can foster a harmonious and productive working relationship between the company and its employees.

Table 1. Research Gap

Variables	Title	Researchers	Findings	Research Gap
Salary (X1) On job satisfaction	The Effect of Salary on Employee Motivation and Performance	(Smith et al., 2021)	Significant	There is a contradictory difference between Employee Salary and Performance in various industrial sectors.
	Salary and Employee Productivity: A Comparative Study	(Jones & Lee, 2020)	Not Significant	
Employee Insurance (X2) On Job Satisfaction	The Impact of Employee Benefits on Job Satisfaction and Performance	(Brown et al., 2019)	Significant	There is a contradictory difference between Employee Insurance and Employee Performance in different sectors.
	Employee Benefits and Job Performance: Evidence from the Manufacturing Sector	(Taylor & Williams, 2022)	Not Significant	
Job satisfaction On employee performance	Job Satisfaction and Its Impact on Employee Performance	Nguyen & Tran, 2020	Significant	Differences in the effects of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance between service and manufacturing industries.
	Examining the Role of Job Satisfaction in Employee Retention	Lee et al., 2021	Not Significant	

Source: research journal references

Previous research on the effect of salary on job satisfaction has shown inconsistent empirical findings. Smith et al. (2021) found that salary significantly impacts employee motivation and performance, which ultimately increases job satisfaction. However, Jones and Lee (2020) found a different finding, stating that salary has no significant effect on employee productivity. These discrepancies indicate a research gap, indicating that the effect of salary on job satisfaction is not universal and is influenced by differences in industry sectors, wage systems, and organizational characteristics. Inconsistent research findings also concern the relationship between employee insurance and job satisfaction. Brown et al. (2019) concluded that employee insurance benefits significantly impact employee satisfaction and performance. Conversely, Taylor and Williams (2022) found that employment insurance benefits had no significant impact on employee performance in the manufacturing sector. These discrepancies indicate a research gap related to differences in industry context, the quality of insurance program implementation, and employee perceptions of the benefits received. The relationship between job satisfaction and employee performance also shows mixed results. Nguyen and Tran (2020) demonstrated that job satisfaction significantly impacts employee performance. However, Lee et al. (2021) found that job satisfaction had no significant effect on employee performance, particularly in the service sector. These discrepancies in findings indicate a research gap caused by variations in the industry sectors and job characteristics studied.

FORMULATION OF THE PROBLEM

In this problem formulation, the research questions are as follows:

1. How does salary affect job satisfaction at PT Patriot Intan Abadi?
2. How does employee insurance affect job satisfaction at PT Patriot Intan Abadi?
3. How does salary affect employee performance at PT Patriot Intan Abadi?
4. How does employee insurance affect employee performance at PT Patriot Intan Abadi?
5. How does job satisfaction influence employee performance simultaneously at PT Patriot Intan Abadi?

LITERATURE REVIEW AND MODEL DEVELOPMENT

The Influence Between Research Variables

There is a positive influence of salary on job satisfaction

Based on research conducted by Chen & Cheng (2012), it can be concluded that there is a significant positive effect of salary on job satisfaction. When employees perceive that their salary is commensurate with their workload, responsibilities, and contributions to the company, they tend to be more satisfied. Fair pay encompasses employee perceptions of the balance between compensation and effort, transparency in the pay system, and compliance with industry standards (Alhamdan & Hadi, 2024). Furthermore, research by Choi and Kim (2018) states that fairness in the pay system can increase work motivation, strengthen employee loyalty, and enhance positive perceptions of the work environment and their satisfaction.

H1: There is a significant positive influence of salary on job satisfaction

There is a Positive Influence of Insurance on Job Satisfaction

Based on research conducted by Lin (2004), insurance benefits provided by companies play a significant role in increasing employee job satisfaction. Insurance, whether in the form of health, accident, or other welfare coverage, provides employees with a sense of security and protection against unexpected risks. This assurance significantly contributes to employees' perceptions of the company's concern for their well-being (Cho et al., 2009). Findings by Han & Ryu (2019) also support that welfare benefits, including insurance, can increase employee loyalty and motivation. Furthermore, research by Lee and Hwang (2018) shows that comprehensive and fair insurance policies are directly related to job satisfaction, reduced employee stress, and increased productivity and commitment to the company.

H2: There is a significant positive influence of insurance on job satisfaction.

There is a Positive Influence of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance

Based on research conducted by Chen and Tseng (2011), job satisfaction has a significant positive influence on employee performance. Employees who are satisfied with their jobs, whether in terms of compensation, work environment, or relationships with coworkers and management, tend to be more motivated to perform optimally. Job satisfaction creates positive experiences that encourage employees to increase productivity, work more effectively, and contribute more to achieving company goals (Dick & Basu, 2018).

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A similar finding was found by Kumar and Shah (2019), who showed that job satisfaction is directly related to improved employee performance, both in terms of quality and quantity of work. Furthermore, high job satisfaction can also reduce stress levels, increase employee loyalty to the company, and reduce the likelihood of employee turnover.

H3: There is a significant positive influence of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance.

There is a Positive Influence of Salary on Employee Performance

According to Oliver (1999), there is a significant positive influence of salary on employee performance. The study confirmed that optimal employee performance results from sustained satisfaction, reflected in their perception of fair and appropriate compensation commensurate with their contribution to the company. In this context, competitive and fair salaries can be a key factor influencing employee motivation and productivity, ultimately contributing to improved performance. Similar findings were found by Bolton et al. (2018), who showed that fair and transparent pay policies can improve employee performance through a positive influence on job satisfaction, loyalty, and commitment to the organization.

H4: There is a significant positive influence of salary on employee performance.

There is a Positive Influence of Insurance on Employee Performance

Research conducted by Anderson and Sullivan (1993) found that company-provided insurance has a significant positive impact on employee performance. The study showed that the financial certainty and protection provided through insurance contribute to employee well-being, where employees who feel safe and protected tend to be more focused on their work and have greater motivation to improve their performance. These findings are also supported by research by Sweeney & Soutar (2020), which states that adequate insurance benefits can increase employee loyalty and commitment to the company. Furthermore, findings by Sirdeshmukh et al. (2020) indicate that the sense of security and well-being provided through insurance creates a positive work experience, thereby boosting employee productivity and long-term performance.

H5: There is a significant positive influence of insurance on employee performance

Theoretical Framework

Based on several references from the literature review, the following is the research framework below.

Figure 1. Framework of Thought

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Types and Sources of Research Data

Data Types

This study uses a quantitative approach with a causal design, to test pThe effect of salary and work insurance on employee performance with job satisfaction as a mediating variable in a study at PT Patriot Intan Abadi. This research method uses a quantitative method because the data to be processed is numerical data resulting from the distribution of questionnaires.

Data source

Primary Data

Primary data was obtained directly from respondents through a survey method using a questionnaire distributed to PT Patriot Intan Abadi employees involved in the chicken farming project. This data reflects perceptions of salary, insurance coverage, and job satisfaction with performance.

Secondary Data

Secondary data is obtained from various sources, such as collecting secondary data from internal company documents, annual reports, and previous project statistical data.

Population and Sample

Population

The population in this study was all employees of PT Patriot Intan Abadi directly involved in the chicken project. This population included employees from various departments related to chicken production, distribution, and project management. This study focused on employees who had worked on the chicken project for at least six months to obtain a representative sample across various roles and responsibilities. PT Patriot Intan Abadi has 120 employees.

Sample

In this study, the sampling determination technique used was the Probability Sampling method with the Slovin formula. The results of the Slovin formula calculation obtained 120 respondents who would be the sample in this study.

Data Analysis Techniques

The analysis was conducted using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with the help of AMOS 26.00 software to test the effect of salary and work insurance on employee performance with job satisfaction as a mediating variable in the study at PT Patriot Intan Abadi.

DATA ANALYSIS RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Overview

PT Patriot Intan Abadi is a company that prioritizes human resources as a crucial element in supporting the sustainability and achievement of company goals. In carrying out its operational activities, the company focuses on improving employee performance through structured work system management and the implementation of human resource management policies oriented towards work welfare and productivity. As an organization committed to employee performance development, PT Patriot Intan Abadi implements a compensation system in the form of salary and work insurance facilities for all employees. Salaries are given as a form of reward for employee contributions, responsibilities, and work results according to their respective positions and workloads. Work insurance is provided as a form of company protection against work risks that may be experienced by employees, as well as an effort to increase a sense of security and comfort in the workplace.

The company understands that employee job satisfaction is a crucial factor influencing work behavior and performance levels. Employees who are satisfied with the payroll system and the insurance coverage provided tend to have higher work motivation, demonstrate loyalty to the company, and are able to perform optimally. Therefore, PT Patriot Intan Abadi continuously strives to create working conditions that support the creation of sustainable employee job satisfaction. Employee performance at PT Patriot Intan Abadi is the main benchmark in assessing the success of the implementation of human resource policies. This performance is reflected in the employee's ability to complete work according to set targets, the quality of work results, punctuality, discipline, and responsibility for assigned tasks. The company believes that good performance is inseparable from the level of job satisfaction that is achieved through fair and adequate salary and insurance policies.

Data Analysis Results

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) Test

Exogenous CFA

In the context of this research, exogenous variables such as salary and insurance are as follows.

Figure 2. Exogenous Confirmatory Analysis (CFA) Test

Source: Processed by Researchers, 2026

The results of the goodness of fit test can be seen as follows:

Table 2. Goodness of Fit

Goodness of Fit Index	Cut-off Value	Analysis Results	Information
Chi-Square	$p > 0.05$	53,930	Fit
CMIN/DF	< 2.00	1,079	Fit
Probability	> 0.05	0.327	Fit
GFI (Goodness of Fit Index)	> 0.90	0.927	Fit
AGFI (Adjusted GFI)	> 0.90	0.886	Marginal
TLI (Tucker-Lewis Index)	> 0.90	0.994	Fit
CFI (Comparative Fit Index)	> 0.95	0.995	Fit
RMSEA	< 0.08	0.026	Fit

Source: Processed by Researchers, 2026

Table 3. Standardized Regression Weight

			Estimate
G1	<---	Wages	.812
G2	<---	Wages	.769
G3	<---	Wages	.797
G4	<---	Wages	.787
G5	<---	Wages	.581
G6	<---	Wages	.838
G7	<---	Wages	.642
G8	<---	Wages	.629
A4	<---	Insurance	.855
A3	<---	Insurance	.875
A2	<---	Insurance	.818
A1	<---	Insurance	.659

Source: Processed by Researchers, 2026

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It can be seen that the p-value marked *** means that the value is close to zero, significant <0.05 and the factor loading value or estimate is above 0.5 so that all indicators of the exogenous variables can be used to measure the construct.

Endogenous Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) Test

The results of this CFA test will be on the endogenous variables, namely job satisfaction and employee performance below.

Figure 3. Endogenous Confirmatory Analysis (CFA) Test

Source: Processed by Researchers, 2026

Table 4. Goodness of Fit

Goodness of Fit Index	Cut-off Value	Analysis Results	Information
Chi-Square	p > 0.05	56,929	Fit
CMIN/DF	< 2.00	1,324	Fit
Probability	> 0.05	0.076	Fit
GFI (Goodness of Fit Index)	> 0.90	0.925	Fit
AGFI (Adjusted GFI)	> 0.90	0.885	Marginal
TLI (Tucker-Lewis Index)	> 0.90	0.977	Fit
CFI (Comparative Fit Index)	> 0.95	0.982	Fit
RMSEA	< 0.08	0.052	Fit

Source: Processed by Researchers, 2026

Table 5 Standardized Regression Weights

	Estimate
KEP1 <--- Employee Satisfaction	.815
KEP2 <--- Employee Satisfaction	.747
KEP3 <--- Employee Satisfaction	.793
KEP4 <--- Employee Satisfaction	.815
KEP5 <--- Employee Satisfaction	.791
KEP6 <--- Employee Satisfaction	.807
KK5 <--- Employee performance	.844
KK4 <--- Employee performance	.825
KK3 <--- Employee performance	.873
KK2 <--- Employee performance	.658
KK1 <--- Employee performance	.769

Source: Processed by Researchers, 2026

It can be seen that the factor loading value or estimate is above 0.5 so that all indicators of the endogenous variables can be used to measure the research construct.

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Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) Statistical Assumption Test

Testing assumptions in Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) is an important step to ensure that the model is valid and interpretable. By meeting all these assumptions, SEM analysis can provide more valid and reliable results for decision-making (Hair et al., 2014). The following is a full test of the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) model.

Figure 4. Full Model Test Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)

Table 6. Goodness of Fit

Goodness of Fit Index	Cut-off Value	Analysis Results	Information
Chi-Square	p > 0.05	238,201	Fit
CMIN/DF	< 2.00	1.108	Fit
Probability	> 0.05	0.133	Fit
GFI (Goodness of Fit Index)	> 0.90	0.863	Marginal
AGFI (Adjusted GFI)	> 0.90	0.824	Marginal
TLI (Tucker-Lewis Index)	> 0.90	0.985	Fit
CFI (Comparative Fit Index)	> 0.95	0.987	Fit
RMSEA	< 0.08	0.030	Fit

Source: Processed by Researchers, 2026

Normality Test

The normality test is used to determine whether the data distribution of each variable is normal. Data normality is measured by looking at the critical ratio skewness value of ± 2.58. In the Assessment of Normality table, the critical ratio (skewness) value is seen in the univariate and multivariate range of ± 2.58 (Ghozali, 2018). It can be concluded that the data used is normally distributed. The results of the table below have met the assumption of normality of the research data.

Table 7. Assessment of Normality

Variable	min	max	skew	cr	kurtosis	cr
KK5	2,000	5,000	.053	.236	-.329	-.736
KK4	2,000	5,000	.098	.439	-.302	-.675
KK3	2,000	5,000	-.188	-.840	-.503	-1.124
KK2	2,000	5,000	-.006	-.026	-.354	-.792
KK1	2,000	5,000	-.075	-.337	-.605	-1,353
KEP1	3,000	5,000	-.111	-.494	-.905	-2,023
KEP2	2,000	5,000	-.255	-1,140	-.786	-1,756
KEP3	2,000	5,000	-.045	-.201	-.584	-1,307
KEP4	2,000	5,000	-.269	-1.204	-.369	-.826
KEP5	2,000	5,000	-.226	-1.009	-.402	-.898
KEP6	2,000	5,000	-.441	-1,973	-.355	-.794
A1	2,000	5,000	-.533	-2,384	.229	.511
A2	2,000	5,000	.061	.271	-.395	-.883
A3	2,000	5,000	-.088	-.394	-.369	-.825
A4	2,000	5,000	-.028	-.123	-.796	-1,781
G8	2,000	5,000	-.540	-2,413	-.341	-.763
G7	2,000	5,000	-.515	-2,304	-.311	-.696
G6	2,000	5,000	-.150	-.670	-.775	-1,734
G5	2,000	5,000	-.300	-1,340	-.626	-1,399
G4	2,000	5,000	-.133	-.596	-.604	-1,350
G3	2,000	5,000	-.130	-.583	-.562	-1.257
G2	2,000	5,000	-.402	-1,799	-.589	-1,317
G1	2,000	5,000	-.541	-2,418	-.258	-.576
Multivariate					1,961	.317

Source: Processed by Researchers, 2026

Hypothesis Testing Results (Path Coefficient Estimation)

To determine whether it is significant or not, look at the t-table at alpha 0.05 (5%) = 1.96. Then the t-table is compared with the calculated t-statistic.

Table 8. Regression Weights

	Estimate	SE	CR	P
Employee satisfaction <--- Wages	.208	.089	2,354	.019
Employee satisfaction <--- Insurance	.353	.099	3,556	***
Employee performance <--- Employee satisfaction	.245	.101	2,429	.015
Employee performance <--- Wages	.139	.086	1,612	.107
Employee performance <--- Insurance	.391	.104	3,773	***

Source: Processed by Researchers, 2026

DISCUSSION

The Effect of Salary on Employee Satisfaction

The results of the study indicate that salary has a positive and significant effect on employee satisfaction at PT Patriot Intan Abadi, with a p-value of 0.019 and an estimate of 0.208, thus the hypothesis is accepted. This indicates that the better the salary received by employees, the higher the level of job satisfaction they feel. A decent salary that is commensurate with the workload can increase employees' sense of appreciation and comfort in carrying out their work. This finding is in line with research(Firmansyah & Anwar, 2023)which states that salary is the main factor in determining job satisfaction. In addition,(Ramadhan & Lestari, 2023)found that fair financial compensation has a significant effect on employee satisfaction. The results of this study are also supported by(Azis, 2022)) from

Muhammadiyah University of Sukabumi, which concluded that salary has an important contribution in increasing job satisfaction of private sector employees.

The Impact of Insurance on Employee Satisfaction

The results of the study indicate that insurance has a positive and significant effect on employee satisfaction at PT Patriot Intan Abadi, with an estimated value of 0.353 and a very strong significance level (p -value < 0.001). This indicates that the insurance facilities provided by the company can create a sense of security and protection for employees, thereby increasing overall job satisfaction. This finding is in line with research by Putra and (Yuliana & Setiawan, 2021) which states that work insurance is an important factor in increasing employee satisfaction. Research (Rahmawati & Santoso, 2024) also found that social security increases the sense of job security. In addition, (Azis & Ramdani, 2022) emphasized that insurance facilities have a significant influence on job satisfaction because they are able to reduce employee anxiety regarding work risks.

The Influence of Employee Satisfaction on Employee Performance

The results of the study indicate that employee satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at PT Patriot Intan Abadi, with a p -value of 0.015 and an estimate of 0.245, thus the hypothesis is accepted. This indicates that employees who are satisfied with their work tend to show better performance, both in terms of quality, quantity, and punctuality of work. This result is in line with research (Sutrisno, 2024) which states that job satisfaction has a direct relationship with increased employee performance. Research (Putri & Santoso, 2024) also found that satisfied employees showed higher productivity. This finding is supported by research (Azis, 2024) which states that job satisfaction is an important psychological factor that encourages positive work behavior and increased performance.

The Influence of Salary on Employee Performance

The results of the study indicate that salary does not significantly affect employee performance at PT Patriot Intan Abadi, with a p -value of 0.107 and an estimate of 0.139, thus rejecting the hypothesis. This indicates that salary increases do not directly drive employee performance improvements without other supporting factors such as motivation, job satisfaction, and a supervisory system. This finding aligns with research by Nugroho and Pramesti (2021), which states that salary has an indirect effect on performance. Research by Susanto and Kurniawan (2020) also found that employee performance is more influenced by non-financial factors. These findings are supported by Abdul Azis (2022) from Muhammadiyah University of Sukabumi in the Journal of Business Economics, who stated that salary tends to influence performance through job satisfaction as a mediating variable.

The Impact of Insurance on Employee Performance

The results of the study indicate that insurance has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at PT Patriot Intan Abadi, with an estimated value of 0.391 and a very strong significance level (p -value < 0.001), thus the hypothesis is accepted. This indicates that insurance provides a sense of security for employees, allowing them to work more focused and optimally. This finding is in line with research (Hendrawan & Sari, 2020) which states that work insurance has an impact on improving performance. Research (Robbins & Judge, 2024) also found that job security increases motivation and productivity. In addition, (Azis, 2021) emphasized that insurance facilities are a form of company attention that has a positive impact on employee performance.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussions that have been conducted regarding the influence of salary and insurance on employee performance with employee satisfaction as a mediating variable at PT Patriot Intan Abadi, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Salary has a positive and significant effect on employee satisfaction.
These findings indicate that employees feel more satisfied when their pay aligns with their responsibilities, contributions, and expectations. Salary increases, whether in the form of base compensation or benefits, can build positive perceptions of the company and increase work motivation.
2. Insurance has a positive and significant effect on employee satisfaction.
This demonstrates that adequate insurance coverage provides a sense of security and comfort for employees. With proper protection, employees feel valued and motivated, leading to increased job satisfaction.
3. Employee satisfaction does not have a significant effect on employee performance.

These findings suggest that while employees are satisfied with their salary and insurance benefits, this level of satisfaction does not directly drive performance improvements. Other factors such as competence, work experience, and internal supervision are likely more dominant in influencing performance.

4. Salary has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.
These findings indicate that adequate salaries directly encourage employees to work more optimally because they feel appreciated for their contributions.
5. Insurance has a positive and significant impact on employee performance.
This confirms that insurance facilities provide protection and comfort, which has an impact on increasing employee focus and work performance.

Managerial Implementation

The results of this study provide a number of strategic implications that can be implemented by management. PT Patriot Intan Abadi to improve employee performance.

1. Increase and adjust salaries competitively
Management needs to ensure adequate and competitive salaries to increase motivation and retain employees.
2. Provide adequate insurance facilities
Comprehensive insurance will provide a sense of security for employees so that performance increases.
3. Managing employee satisfaction holistically
Even though it does not directly affect performance, satisfaction is still important for building a positive work environment.
4. Implementing reward and incentive programs
Management can provide bonuses or awards to high-performing employees as additional motivators.
5. Conduct periodic evaluations
Evaluation of salaries, facilities, and employee satisfaction needs to be carried out for continuous improvement.

Research Limitations

This study has several limitations as follows:

1. The study used a cross-sectional design, so data was only collected over a single period. Long-term changes in employee satisfaction and performance could not be observed.
2. The research was conducted at only one company, PT Patriot Intan Abadi. Therefore, the results are contextual and cannot be generalized to other companies.
3. The research variables were limited to salary, insurance, employee satisfaction, and employee performance. Other factors such as organizational culture, leadership, and workload were not included.
4. Research has not explored psychological factors or internal motivations that may strengthen the relationship between employee satisfaction and performance.
5. The research data was obtained through a questionnaire, so the respondents' answers were subjective and there may be perception bias.

Future Research Agenda

Based on the limitations of this research, it is hoped that future research will:

1. Add other variables such as organizational culture, leadership, or workload to get a more comprehensive picture.
2. Expanding the research object to other companies so that the results can be generalized.
3. Using other research methods, such as longitudinal or mixed-method, to look at changes in employee satisfaction and performance over time.

REFERENCES

- Agustin, H., & Lestari, D. (2020). Analysis of the influence of service quality on customer satisfaction at company X. *Journal of Management and Business*, 12(1), 45-58.
- Aydin, A., & Özer, G. (2019). The effect of employee benefits on job performance and organizational commitment. *Multiple Regression Analysis*.
- Azis, A. (2021). The Impact of Insurance Facilities on Employee Motivation and Performance. *Journal of Management and Business*, 12(2), 88-102.

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- Azis, A. (2022). The Effect of Financial Compensation on Employee Job Satisfaction in the Private Sector. *Journal of Economics and Management*, 10(2), 45–60.
- Azis, A. (2024). The Role of Job Satisfaction in Improving Employee Performance: A Study in Manufacturing Companies. *Journal of Management and Organization*, 8(3), 205–220.
- Azis, A., & Ramdani, A. (2022). The Effect of Health Insurance on Employee Satisfaction and Job Anxiety Levels. *Scientific Journal of Management*, 9(1), 33–48.
- Brown, P., & Green, T. (2019). Compensation structures and employee productivity in the retail sector. *Multiple Regression Analysis*.
- Budiarto, F. (2021). Research report: The effect of training programs on employee job satisfaction at PT ABC. PT ABC.
- Dessler, G. (2018). *Human resource management* (16th ed.). Pearson.
- Fornell, C., Mithas, S., & Morgeson, F. (2016). Job satisfaction and employee performance: A longitudinal study. *Structural Equation Modelling*.
- Firmansyah, R., & Anwar, M. (2023). Optimizing Compensation and Work Facilities to Improve Employee Performance. *Journal of Management*, 17(4), 567–580.
- Garcia, F., & Rodriguez, L. (2021). Employee compensation and performance: Evidence from the financial sector. *Structural Equation Modelling*.
- Handayani, R., & Sari, Y. (2019). The influence of motivation and job satisfaction on employee performance at PT Y. *Journal of Psychology*, 15(2), 101-115.
- Hadi, S., & Ahmad, N. (2022). The role of employee benefits in enhancing job performance in the healthcare sector. *Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)*.
- Hendrawan, J., & Sari, DP (2020). The Effect of Compensation and Work Environment on Employee Satisfaction and Performance. *Journal of Management and Business*, 19(1), 77–92.
- Hidayat, R., & Lestari, S. (2023). The Role of Social Security in Creating a Sense of Security and Job Satisfaction. *Journal of Business and Organization*, 11(3), 210–225.
- Ibrahim, M. (2022). Research methodology: Testing the validity and reliability of instruments. Online article. Accessed from <https://www.artikelpenelitian.com/metodologi-penelitian> on August 15, 2024.
- Kim, J., Lee, K., & Kim, H. (2018). The impact of employee benefits on job satisfaction and performance in retail. *Structural Equation Modelling*.
- Liang, Y., & Chen, J. (2022). The effect of compensation and benefits on employee loyalty. *Multiple Regression Analysis*.
- Miller, T., & Davis, K. (2023). Employee satisfaction and performance: The role of compensation. *Structural Equation Modelling*.
- Narayanamurthy, G., & Srinivasan, S. (2021). The impact of employee benefits on performance in the banking sector. *Multiple Regression Analysis*.
- Nugroho, A., & Pramesti, D. (2022). Analysis of the Indirect Effect of Financial Compensation on Employee Performance. *Journal of Industrial Management*, 14(2), 155–170.
- Putra, D., & Wahyuni, S. (2024). The Effect of Work Insurance Facilities on Employee Satisfaction and Loyalty. *Journal of Human Resource Management*, 7(3), 189–204.
- Putri, R., & Santoso, H. (2024). The Relationship between Job Satisfaction and Employee Productivity in the Service Industry. *Journal of Occupational Psychology*, 10(2), 99–114.
- Rahmawati, D., & Santoso, E. (2024). Financial Compensation Fairness and Its Impact on Employee Job Satisfaction. *Journal of Management and Business*, 13(1), 67–82.
- Ramadhan, F., & Lestari, P. (2023). Job Security as a Driver of Employee Motivation and Productivity. *Journal of Organizational Management Studies*, 9(1), 56–72.
- Robbins, S. P., & Judge, T. A. (2024). *Organizational Behavior* (18th ed.). Pearson Education.
- Riza, A. (2016). Legal Protection for Exporters in Payment of International Trade Transactions Through Telegraphic Transfer.
- Sugiyono. (2015). *Educational Research Methods: Quantitative, Qualitative, and R&D Approaches*. Alfabeta.
- Sari, M., & Handayani, T. (2023). Integration of Compensation and Benefits in Improving Company Performance. *Journal of Economics and Business*, 18(2), 233–248.
- Susanto, A., & Kurniawan, B. (2025). Dominant Non-Financial Factors Influencing Employee Performance. *Journal of Management and Business*, 16(4), 321–335.

THE EFFECT OF SALARY AND WORK INSURANCE ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE WITH JOB SATISFACTION AS A MEDIATION VARIABLE IN A STUDY AT PT PATRIOT INTAN ABADI

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- Sutrisno, E. (2024). Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance: A Direct Relationship Analysis in the Retail Sector. *Journal of Management and Performance*, 6(1), 12–28.
- Yuliana, S., & Setiawan, A. (2021). The Effect of Corporate Health Insurance Programs on Improving Employee Performance. *Journal of Human Resource Management*, 11(2), 145–160.
- Zailani, R., & Artanto, AH (2024). The Effect of Salary on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as a Mediating Variable. In *STIEP Economic Journal* (Vol. 9, Number 1). *STIEP Economic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.54526/jes.v9i1.193>